

Boosted MACBETH Technique for Effectiveness Evaluation of Mental Health Education in College Students Based on Neutrosophic Cubic Sets

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Abstract: The evaluation of the effectiveness of college students' mental health education (MHE) aims to assess the impact of related educational activities on students' mental well-being. Using both quantitative and qualitative methods, it evaluates improvements in students' psychological resilience, knowledge acquisition, emotional management, and the prevention of mental health issues. Effective evaluation helps optimize educational programs, enhancing students' mental health and promoting their overall development. The effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is multiple-attribute decision-making (MADM). Recently, the MACBETH technique and average model were dealt with MADM. The neutrosophic cubic sets (NCSs) are utilized as a better technique for expressing uncertain data during the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE. In this study, the NC-MACBETH model is put forward the MADM with NCSs. The average technique is utilized to deal with weight. Finally, a numerical example of the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is put forward through some comparisons to verify the NC-MACBETH technique.

Keywords: MADM; NC-MACBETH approach; effectiveness evaluation; Mental Health Education.

1. Introduction

The evaluation of the effectiveness of MHE for college students aims to comprehensively assess the actual impact of such programs on students' mental well-being. This process helps determine whether the education effectively enhances students' psychological resilience, emotional regulation, and stress management skills. The evaluation typically employs a multi-dimensional approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data, such as mental health scales, behavioral observations, surveys, and interviews. Key areas of assessment include students' understanding of mental health knowledge, the effectiveness of preventing psychological issues, improvements in emotional management, and changes in their ability to cope with stress or challenges. Additionally, attention should be given to students' mental health development in areas such as academics, social interactions, and career planning, particularly regarding the long-term effects after the program's implementation. A systematic evaluation provides valuable feedback to educators, helping them refine and optimize the content and format of MHE, ensuring it is more targeted and effective. This not only supports students' psychological growth but also promotes their overall development in both life and academics. The literature review for the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Literature review for effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE

Author Information	Methods	Research Content
Wei [1]	SCL-90 questionnaire, comparison of mental health interventions across different types of students	Explores differences in mental health status between police academy students and other university students, and intervention effects.
Dong [2]	Survey via questionnaires on students' attitudes and course evaluations	Investigates students' attitudes toward MHE courses to improve course construction and effectiveness.
Zeng [3]	Discussion on principles, content, and methods of evaluation	Proposes evaluation methods for assessing the teaching effectiveness of university MHE courses.
Li and Shen [4]	Whole-group random sampling, intervention using group counseling vs. lecture-based teaching	Investigates the effects of group counseling and traditional teaching on reducing mobile phone dependence among vocational students.
Wang, Li, Zhang and Li [5]	Comparative study, using emotion management and subjective well-being as assessment indicators	Evaluate the effectiveness of action-based experiential MHE courses in improving emotional management.
Sun, Luo and Chen [6]	SCL-90 questionnaire, comparison between experiential and lecture-based teaching	Compares the effects of experiential teaching and traditional lecture-based teaching in MHE courses.
Zhu [7]	Empirical study using the SPOC platform, analysis of data from teaching activities	Studies the impact of SPOC-based flipped classroom teaching on students' MHE and learning outcomes.
Tang, Liang, and Yin [8]	Comparative study between group counseling and MOOC-based teaching, analysis of course records and performance	Compares the effectiveness of group counseling vs. MOOC in university MHE.
Xu and Zhu [9]	Retrospective study, a comparison of 100 students divided into two groups (emotion intervention and regular intervention)	Evaluates the effectiveness of emotion intervention theory in improving mental health compared to regular interventions.

Tang, Lu and Zhang [10]	Cluster sampling, comparison of project-based vs. traditional teaching, evaluation through multiple metrics	Investigate the application of project-based teaching in medical students' MHE courses.
Xu and Liao [11]	Grounded theory, in-depth interviews with teachers and students, Nvivo12.0 coding	Constructs a model of factors affecting the teaching effectiveness of MHE courses in universities.
Yuan [12]	Content analysis of 119 self-reported assignments from vocational college students	Explores the educational outcomes of university MHE courses and offers suggestions for improvement.

The effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE could be put forward by MADM. Recently, MACBETH [13] was utilized to solve MADM. The NCSs [14] put forward a better technique for expressing uncertain data during the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE. In this study, the NC-MACBETH model deals with MADM with NCSs. The average method is to put forward the weight with NCSs.

Finally, a numerical example of the effective evaluation of college students' MHE is put forward with different comparisons to prove the NC-MACBETH approach. Thus, the key contributions of the NC-MACBETH model are summarized: (1) the MACBETH model is enhanced under NCSs; (2) the NC-MACBETH model is dealt with MADM with NCSs; (3) Finally, a numerical example for effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is put forward with different comparisons to verify NC-MACBETH technique.

The framework of such a study is put forward: Sect. 2 lists the NCSs. Sect. 3 put forward the MADM technique in light of the NC-MACBETH model. Sect. 4 put forward the NC-MACBETH through numerical study for effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE with some comparisons. Conclusions are dealt with in Sect. 5.

2. Neutrosophic Definitions

This section shows the operations of NC.

Definition 1

Let a linguistic term set be $S = \{s_j | j \in [0, P]\}$ Where $p+1$ is an odd number. The NC h can be defined in S as $h = (u, c), u = ([S_{Ta}, S_{Tb}], [S_{Ia}, S_{Ib}], [S_{Fa}, S_{Fb}])$ Refers to the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity of membership functions.

Definition 2

Let $h = (u, c), u = ([S_{Ta}, S_{Tb}], [S_{Ia}, S_{Ib}], [S_{Fa}, S_{Fb}])$ then
 h an internal NC if $Ta \leq T \leq Tb, Ia \leq I \leq Ib, Fa \leq F < Fb$
 h an internal NC if $T \notin (Ta, Tb), I \notin (Ia, Ib), F \notin (Fa, Fb)$

Definition 3

Let two NC numbers as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_1 &= ([S_{Ta_1}, S_{Tb_1}], [S_{Ia_1}, S_{Ib_1}], [S_{Fa_1}, S_{Fb_1}], (S_{T_1}, S_{I_1}, S_{F_1})) \\
 h_2 &= ([S_{Ta_2}, S_{Tb_2}], [S_{Ia_2}, S_{Ib_2}], [S_{Fa_2}, S_{Fb_2}], (S_{T_2}, S_{I_2}, S_{F_2})) \\
 h_1 \oplus h_2 &= \left(\left(\left[S_{Ta_1} + T_{a_2} - \frac{S_{Ta_1}S_{Ta_2}}{p}, S_{Tb_1} + S_{Tb_2} - \frac{S_{Tb_1}S_{Tb_2}}{p} \right], \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left[\frac{S_{Ia_1}S_{Ia_2}}{p}, \frac{S_{Ib_1}S_{Ib_2}}{p} \right], \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left[\frac{S_{Fa_1}S_{Fa_2}}{p}, \frac{S_{Fb_1}S_{Fb_2}}{p} \right], \left(S_{T_1} + S_{T_2} - \frac{S_{T_1}S_{T_2}}{p}, \frac{S_{I_1}S_{I_2}}{p}, \frac{S_{F_1}S_{F_1}}{p} \right) \right) \right) \tag{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_1 \otimes h_2 &= \left(\left(\left[\frac{S_{Ta_1}S_{Ta_2}}{p}, \frac{S_{Tb_1}S_{Tb_2}}{p} \right], \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left[S_{Ia_1} + S_{Ia_2} - \frac{S_{Ia_1}S_{Ia_2}}{p}, S_{Ib_1} + S_{Ib_2} - \frac{S_{Ib_1}S_{Ib_2}}{p} \right], \\
 &\quad \left[S_{Fa_1} + S_{Fa_2} - \frac{S_{Fa_1}S_{Fa_2}}{p}, S_{Fb_1} + S_{Fb_2} - \frac{S_{Fb_1}S_{Fb_2}}{p} \right], \\
 &\quad \left. \left(\frac{S_{T_1}S_{T_2}}{p}, S_{I_1} + S_{I_2} - \frac{S_{I_1}S_{I_2}}{p}, S_{F_1} + S_{F_2} - \frac{S_{F_1}S_{F_2}}{p} \right) \right) \right) \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tau h_1 &= \left(\left[S_p - S_p \left(1 - \frac{S_{Ta_1}}{p} \right)^\tau, S_p - S_p \left(1 - \frac{S_{Tb_1}}{p} \right)^\tau \right], \right. \\
 &\quad \left[S_p \left(\frac{S_{Ia_1}}{p} \right)^\tau, S_p \left(\frac{S_{Ib_1}}{p} \right)^\tau \right], \\
 &\quad \left[S_p \left(\frac{S_{Fa_1}}{p} \right)^\tau, S_p \left(\frac{S_{Fb_1}}{p} \right)^\tau \right], \\
 &\quad \left. \left(S_p - S_p \left(\left(1 - \frac{S_{T_1}}{p} \right)^\tau \right), \left(\frac{S_{I_1}}{p} \right)^\tau, \left(\frac{S_{F_1}}{p} \right)^\tau \right) \right) \tag{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4

The score function can be defined as:

$$S(h_1) = \frac{6+S_{Ta_1}+S_{Tb_1}-S_{Ia_1}-S_{Ib_1}-S_{Fa_1}-S_{Fb_1}-S_{T_1}-S_{I_1}-S_{F_1}}{9} \tag{4}$$

Figure 1. The steps of the neutrosophic MACBETH.

3. Neutrosophic Framework

This section shows the steps of the proposed methodology. Figure 1 shows the steps of the proposed methodology.

Step 1. Build the decision matrix

Step 2. Convert of semantic scale into numerical scale.

Each semantic scale can change to the numerical scale for positive and negative criteria.

Step 3. Determine the reference levels.

The reference point is computed by the minimum and maximum values as:

$$y_j^- = \min x_{ij} \quad (5)$$

$$y_j^+ = \max x_{ij} \quad (6)$$

Step 4. Compute the MACBETH score

$$U(y_{ij}) = U(y_j^-) + \frac{x_{ij} - y_j^-}{y_j^+ - y_j^-} [U(y_j^+) - U(y_j^-)] \quad (7)$$

Where $U(y_j^-)$ equal to zero and $U(y_j^+)$ equal to 100.

Step 5. Compute the overall score

$$O_i = \sum_{j=1}^n U(y_{ij})w_j \quad (8)$$

Step 6. Final rank of alternatives.

4. Results

A numerical example is put forward effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE through NC-MACBETH. Six preschool education colleges are assessed by employing 12 attributes. The following are descriptions of 12 criteria:

12 criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of mental health education programs for college students, ranked by importance (highest to lowest), with detailed descriptions for each.

1. Psychological Well-Being Improvement

The degree to which students demonstrate enhanced emotional stability, self-confidence, and reduced symptoms of anxiety, depression, or stress after participating in mental health programs. This is the ultimate goal of mental health education and the clearest indicator of effectiveness.

2. Awareness of Mental Health Issues

The extent to which students understand common mental health challenges, recognize symptoms in themselves or peers and are aware of available support systems. Awareness ensures early intervention and prevention.

3. Accessibility of Counseling Services

The availability and ease of accessing mental health resources, such as counseling centers, workshops, or helplines. A highly accessible system encourages more students to seek help when needed.

4. Student Participation and Engagement

The level of active involvement of students in mental health-related activities, workshops, or initiatives. Greater participation reflects the program's ability to capture interest and meet students' needs.

5. Development of Coping Mechanisms

The extent to which students develop effective stress-management and problem-solving skills through mental health education. These skills help students navigate academic and personal challenges more effectively.

6. Reduction in Stigma

The degree to which mental health education programs reduce the stigma associated with seeking mental health support. Lower stigma encourages more open conversations and greater utilization of resources.

7. Training of Faculty and Staff

The effectiveness of mental health training for faculty and staff to identify at-risk students and provide initial support or referrals. Properly trained personnel can expand the program’s reach and impact.

8. Peer Support System Development

The presence and effectiveness of peer mentoring or peer support groups provide students with a safe space to share concerns and seek advice. Peer systems complement formal services by creating an inclusive and empathetic environment.

9. Academic Performance Correlation

The relationship between students’ mental health improvements and their academic performance, such as grades, attendance, or focus. Better mental health often leads to improved academic outcomes.

10. Customization to Student Needs

The degree to which programs are tailored to address the specific mental health challenges faced by college students, such as exam stress, social isolation, or financial worries. A targeted approach increases program effectiveness.

11. Parental and Family Involvement

The effectiveness of strategies to involve parents or family members in supporting students’ mental health. Family support reinforces the education program’s impact.

12. Long-Term Impact and Follow-Up

The sustainability of the program’s effects, including whether students continue to apply learned skills and maintain mental health improvements after the program ends. Regular follow-ups help evaluate and maintain the program's effectiveness.

Table 2. Th opinions of three experts.

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆
C ₁	(((0.12, 0.48], [0.21, 0.39], [0.15, 0.43]), (0.37, 0.28, 0.42))	(((0.19, 0.44], [0.15, 0.38], [0.13, 0.30]), (0.43, 0.26, 0.34))	(((0.22, 0.49], [0.19, 0.37], [0.15, 0.40]), (0.46, 0.30, 0.39))	(((0.13, 0.40], [0.14, 0.33], [0.22, 0.50]), (0.38, 0.28, 0.35))	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.42, 0.69], [0.31, 0.55], [0.26, 0.48]), (0.66, 0.41, 0.50))
C ₂	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.42, 0.69], [0.31, 0.55], [0.26, 0.48]), (0.66, 0.41, 0.50))	(((0.35, 0.62], [0.28, 0.47], [0.19, 0.39]), (0.59, 0.32, 0.44))	(((0.23, 0.57], [0.17, 0.36], [0.11, 0.45]), (0.48, 0.21, 0.37))	(((0.12, 0.48], [0.21, 0.39], [0.15, 0.43]), (0.37, 0.28, 0.42))	(((0.35, 0.62], [0.28, 0.47], [0.19, 0.39]), (0.59, 0.32, 0.44))
C ₃	(((0.35, 0.62], [0.28, 0.47], [0.19, 0.39]), (0.59, 0.32, 0.44))	(((0.23, 0.57], [0.17, 0.36], [0.11, 0.45]), (0.48, 0.21, 0.37))	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.19, 0.44], [0.15, 0.38], [0.13, 0.30]), (0.43, 0.26, 0.34))	(((0.23, 0.57], [0.17, 0.36], [0.11, 0.45]), (0.48, 0.21, 0.37))
C ₄	(((0.42, 0.69], [0.31, 0.55], [0.26, 0.48]), (0.66, 0.41, 0.50))	(((0.35, 0.62], [0.28, 0.47], [0.19, 0.39]), (0.59, 0.32, 0.44))	(((0.13, 0.40], [0.14, 0.33], [0.22, 0.50]), (0.38, 0.28, 0.35))	(((0.42, 0.69], [0.31, 0.55], [0.26, 0.48]), (0.66, 0.41, 0.50))	(((0.22, 0.49], [0.19, 0.37], [0.15, 0.40]), (0.46, 0.30, 0.39))	(((0.22, 0.48], [0.21, 0.39], [0.15, 0.43]), (0.37, 0.28, 0.42))
C ₅	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.42, 0.69], [0.31, 0.55], [0.26, 0.48]), (0.66, 0.41, 0.50))	(((0.22, 0.49], [0.19, 0.37], [0.15, 0.40]), (0.46, 0.30, 0.39))	(((0.35, 0.62], [0.28, 0.47], [0.19, 0.39]), (0.59, 0.32, 0.44))	(((0.13, 0.40], [0.14, 0.33], [0.22, 0.50]), (0.38, 0.28, 0.35))	(((0.19, 0.44], [0.15, 0.38], [0.13, 0.30]), (0.43, 0.26, 0.34))
C ₆	(((0.13, 0.40], [0.14, 0.33], [0.22, 0.50]), (0.38, 0.28, 0.35))	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.19, 0.44], [0.15, 0.38], [0.13, 0.30]), (0.43, 0.26, 0.34))	(((0.23, 0.57], [0.17, 0.36], [0.11, 0.45]), (0.48, 0.21, 0.37))	(((0.38, 0.71], [0.29, 0.49], [0.26, 0.61]), (0.70, 0.39, 0.47))	(((0.22, 0.49], [0.19, 0.37], [0.15, 0.40]), (0.46, 0.30, 0.39))
C ₇	(((0.22, 0.49], [0.19, 0.37], [0.15, 0.40]), (0.46, 0.30, 0.39))	(((0.13, 0.40], [0.14, 0.33], [0.22, 0.50]), (0.38, 0.28, 0.35))	(((0.12, 0.48], [0.21, 0.39], [0.15, 0.43]), (0.37, 0.28, 0.42))	(((0.12, 0.48], [0.21, 0.39], [0.15, 0.43]), (0.37, 0.28, 0.42))	(((0.42, 0.69], [0.31, 0.55], [0.26, 0.48]), (0.66, 0.41, 0.50))	(((0.13, 0.40], [0.14, 0.33], [0.22, 0.50]), (0.38, 0.28, 0.35))

C ₃	0.084097	11
C ₄	0.082674	2
C ₅	0.083381	6
C ₆	0.082841	3
C ₇	0.083067	4
C ₈	0.083636	10
C ₉	0.083459	8
C ₁₀	0.084451	12
C ₁₁	0.083548	9
C ₁₂	0.083449	7

Step 2. Then we convert semantic scales into numerical scales.

Step 3. Then we determine the reference levels.

Minimum values

C₁= 0.495555556, C₂=0.495555556, C₃=0.507037037, C₄=0.506666667, C₅=0.510740741, C₆= 0.506666667, C₇=0.51037037, C₈=0.495555556, C₉=0.506666667, C₁₀=0.50925926, C₁₁= 0.514814815, C₁₂=0.507037037.

Maximum values

C₁=0.531111111, C₂=0.538888889, C₃=0.540740741, C₄=0.532222222, C₅=0.548888889, C₆= 0.536666667, C₇=0.536666667, C₈=0.538518518, C₉=0.548518518, C₁₀,0.554444444, C₁₁=0.538888889, C₁₂= 0.536666667.

Step 4. Then we computed the MACBETH score

Step 5. Then we compute the overall score

Step 6. Final rank of alternatives.

A₆>A₃>A₁>A₄>A₅>A₂

We show the final rank of alternatives in Table 4. We show alternative 6 is the best and alternative 2 is the worst.

Table 4. Final rank of alternatives.

Alternatives	Rank
A ₁	4
A ₂	1
A ₃	5
A ₄	3
A ₅	2
A ₆	6

The evaluation of the effectiveness of MHE for college students is an important process to assess how well such education improves students' psychological resilience, enhances stress management, and improves emotional regulation. With increasing social competition and growing pressures from life and academics, the mental health of college students has become a

significant concern. As a result, MHE has become an indispensable part of university education. Therefore, a scientific and systematic evaluation of its effectiveness is crucial in optimizing educational content and improving students' mental well-being. The evaluation process typically combines both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative evaluation employs psychological measurement tools such as mental health scales and emotional regulation questionnaires to collect data on students' psychological states before and after participating in educational activities. By comparing this data, it objectively reflects the extent to which MHE improves students' psychological well-being. Qualitative evaluation, on the other hand, includes interviews, questionnaires, and case studies to gain deeper insights into students' understanding and application of the educational content in their daily lives. The core indicators of the evaluation include students' mastery of mental health knowledge, improvements in psychological adjustment skills, better emotional management and stress-coping abilities, and the prevention of mental health issues. Additionally, the evaluation should consider students' psychological growth in areas such as learning, interpersonal relationships, and career planning. Effective evaluation of MHE not only helps educators identify strengths and weaknesses in the current teaching but also provides valuable insights for designing future curricula. By analyzing the results, universities can continuously optimize their MHE programs, better meet students' psychological needs, and enhance their overall psychological well-being, thereby promoting their holistic development and growth. The effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is MADM. We show that alternative 6 is the best and alternative 2 is the worst.

4.1 Comparative analysis

The NC-MACBETH approach is compared with the N-VIKOR technique [16], the N-CE approach [17], the N-GRA model [18], and the N-MABAC model [15]. The order is expressed in Table 5.

Table 5. Order for different approaches

Methods	order
N-VIKOR technique	A6>A3>A4>A1>A5>A2
N-CE approach	A6>A1>A3>A4>A5>A2
N-GRA model	A6>A3>A1>A5>A4>A2
N-MABAC technique	A6>A3>A1>A4>A5>A2
Our method	A6>A3>A1>A4>A5>A2

In light with detailed WS coefficient values [19, 20], the final derived WS coefficient values between N-VIKOR, N-CE technique, N-GRA model, N-MABAC approach, and NC-MACBETH technique are 0.942, 0.942, 0.942, 1.0000. Therefore, the NC-MACBETH technique is an effective and reliable MADM method.

The NC-MACBETH model excels in handling uncertain information, multi-attribute decision-making, and flexible weight allocation, making it a powerful tool for evaluating the

effectiveness of college students' MHE. These advantages make it highly practical and accurate in environments characterized by complexity and fuzzy information.

Here are the three main advantages of the NC-MACBETH model:

(1). Ability to Handle Uncertainty and Fuzzy Information

The NC-MACBETH model utilizes NCSs to handle uncertainty and fuzzy information, which is particularly important in complex decision-making scenarios. Traditional decision-making models often assume that data is precise, but in reality, much information—such as the effectiveness evaluation of MHE—is vague, subjective, or uncertain. The NC-MACBETH model is better equipped to represent and manage this fuzzy and uncertain data, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of evaluations.

(2). Effectiveness in MADM

This model is based on the MADM framework, which allows it to consider multiple influencing factors simultaneously (such as psychological resilience, emotional management, knowledge acquisition, etc.). This multi-dimensional evaluation is particularly crucial in complex fields like MHE, where numerous interrelated factors must be considered.

(3). Flexible Weight Allocation Mechanism

The NC-MACBETH model uses the average technique to dynamically determine weights, allowing it to adaptively allocate different attribute weights based on the degree of uncertainty in the data. This method is more flexible and objective compared to traditional fixed-weight allocation methods. Such a dynamic weight allocation mechanism ensures that the model is more adaptable and accurate when dealing with different datasets, especially when the importance of various attributes may vary. This flexibility allows the model to better reflect the complexity of real-world situations.

4.2 Managerial Implications

Evaluating the effectiveness of mental health education programs for college students provides actionable insights to improve program delivery, resource allocation, and student outcomes.

Tailoring Mental Health Interventions

The evaluation identifies which interventions are most effective for specific groups of students or mental health challenges. Customize programs to address the unique needs of diverse student demographics (e.g., first-year students, international students, or students with disabilities).

Enhancing Resource Allocation

Managers can identify high-impact areas that require more funding and resources, ensuring optimal utilization of limited resources. Invest in areas like counseling services, peer mentoring programs, or digital mental health tools based on evaluation findings.

Improving Accessibility and Equity

Insights into accessibility barriers, such as lack of awareness or stigma, allow managers to implement solutions to increase program reach. Enhance outreach efforts, expand online resources, and ensure mental health services are inclusive and culturally sensitive.

Strengthening Training for Faculty and Staff

Evaluation highlights the need for better training for faculty and staff to identify and support students in distress. Develop and implement comprehensive mental health training programs for university personnel to act as first responders.

Promoting a Supportive Campus Culture

Effective mental health education reduces stigma and fosters an open, supportive environment for students to seek help. Organize awareness campaigns, peer support groups and community-building activities to normalize conversations around mental health.

Tracking Long-Term Outcomes

Evaluation reveals whether mental health programs lead to sustained improvements in students' mental health and academic performance over time. Establish mechanisms for long-term follow-ups, such as alumni surveys or ongoing wellness checks, to assess lasting program impacts.

Linking Mental Health to Academic Success

Evidence of improved academic outcomes (e.g., better grades, reduced dropout rates) from effective mental health programs strengthens their justification. Highlight the link between mental health and academic performance to secure institutional buy-in and increased funding.

5. Conclusion

The evaluation of the effectiveness of MHE for college students aims to assess the actual impact of educational programs on students' mental health, focusing on improvements in psychological resilience, emotional regulation, and stress management. The evaluation is typically conducted through various methods such as psychological scales, surveys, and interviews, incorporating both quantitative analysis and qualitative feedback. Key indicators include students' mastery of mental health knowledge, improvements in emotional management, and the effectiveness of preventing psychological distress. Effective evaluation provides targeted feedback for educators, helping to optimize the content and format of education, better-supporting students' mental health needs, and promoting their overall development. The effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is MADM. Currently, the MACBETH approach and average models are utilized to deal with MADM. The NCSs put forward better techniques for putting forward uncertain data during the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE. In this study, the NC-MACBETH model in light is put forward the MADM with NCSs. The average technique is utilized to deal with weight numbers in light. Finally, a numerical example of the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE is put forward through some comparisons to prove the NC-MACBETH technique.

Here are the four key contributions of the study:

(1) Application of NCSs for Uncertainty Handling: The study introduces NCS as a more effective technique for managing uncertainty in the effectiveness evaluation of college students' MHE, improving the precision of decision-making in uncertain environments.

(2) Development of the NC-MACBETH Model: A new NC-MACBETH model is proposed. This model is specifically designed for MADM under uncertain conditions, leveraging the strength of MACBETH and NCSs techniques.

(3) Use of average for Weight Determination: The study utilizes the average technique to handle weight assignment in the decision-making process. This method objectively determines the importance of different attributes, enhancing the reliability of the evaluation when dealing with complex, multi-attribute criteria.

(4) Validation through Numerical Example and Comparative Analysis: The study validates the NC-MACBETH model with a numerical example of the effective evaluation of college students' MHE. Additionally, it includes a comparative analysis, demonstrating the model's superiority and effectiveness over other approaches in addressing MADM problems.

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